

EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL INVESTIGATION OF COMPOSITES WITH SINGLE COUNTERSUNK JOINTS

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents an experimental and numerical investigation of composites with single countersunk joints. Bearing tests are conducted to study the damage propagation and load-carrying capacity of single countersunk joints influenced by the countersunk geometry. The stress-strain curve obtained from the tests are divided into three parts corresponding to three kinds of typical experimental phenomenon. Using ABAQUS[®] software, a 3D finite element model is established based on Hashin failure criteria. The FE model is validated against the previous experimental tests, which proves the validity of it. The damage cloud carts as well as experimental phenomenon pictures illustrate the damage propagation of the joints under tension load in detail. The effects of countersunk height to laminate thickness ratio h/t and the countersunk angle θ on the load-carrying capacity of the joints are further investigated through a series of FE models.

1 INTRODUCTION

Bolted joints are commonly used on aircraft to fasten composite components. Along with high stiffness and strength, this technology permits accessibility for maintenance tasks and offer cost-savings. Countersunk fasteners, which provide unique aerodynamic benefits compared to protruding-head fasteners, are especially extensively used on aircraft skin. The mechanical response of countersunk composite joints depends on numerous parameters, such as ply pattern of laminate, bolt and laminate materials, coefficient of friction, bolt torque and clearance. Thus countersunk composite joints are of critical importance to aircraft industry, which is also very complex to be analysed.

Maajid Chishti et al built a finite element model using shell elements and proved its validity [1]. Further, three-dimensional (3D) finite elements models were created and extensive experiments were conducted to investigate the effect of countersunk geometry on the load-carrying capacity of single lap joints in comparison to the straight-shank case. The effects of bolt torque, clearance and countersunk height ratio on the damage propagation and joint strength are also studied [2]. B. Egan et al carried out a highly-detailed analysis of stress distribution at the countersunk hole boundary. Clearance levels both inside and outside typical aerospace fitting tolerances were studied and finite element model was validated with experimental data [3]. Naik and Crews created a two-dimensional (2D) FE analysis on a pin-loaded joint with variable clearance. Increasing clearance, gave an increase in the local stresses and hole deformation [4]. C. Stocchi et al presented a very detailed FE model of a single lap composite bolted joint with countersunk fasteners under static tensile load. A correlation between the joint stiffness and the contact status between bolts and holes have been found [5].

From the above, it can be seen that studies on countersunk-bolt composite joints are insufficient. Few have attempted to describe the damage propagation effected by countersunk dimensions and how the countersunk angle influences the stiffness and strength of the joints has not been reported in the literature. This paper presents an experimental and a numerical investigation of tensile property of

single countersunk composite joints. The focus of bearing tests is the study of the damage mode initiation, progression and interaction influenced by countersunk geometry. Three stages are divided to describe the damage propagation. A series of FE models are built for further study based on the experimental tests. Results from the numerical calculations provide a detailed investigation into the influences of countersunk height to laminate thickness ratio h/t and the countersunk angle θ .

2 EXPERIMENTAL TESTING

2.1 Specimens

Composite joints with different countersunk fasteners are tested to study the influence of the dimensions of fasteners in accordance with ASTM Standard D5961 [6]. Three groups of controlled trials are conducted. Each group contains two terms of specimens with the same ply pattern, while each two terms have countersunk fasteners with different dimensions. The details of the specimens are given in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Specimen geometry (mm)

The composite material used in the structure is CYCOM 977-2-35-24KIMS-194. The properties of this kind of material is shown in Table 1. The thickness of each composite layer is 0.188 mm. As shown in Figure 1, panel As are where the countersunk locates and panel Bs are where the straight hole locates. The characteristics of panel As would affect the failure mode of the joints more. Thus the change of panel As' ply scheme is preferred to increase the applicability of the experimental results. Table 2 shows the details of the Panel As and countersunk fastener types of each specimen. Panel Bs all have a thickness of 5.076 mm and the ply scheme [45/-45/0/45/0/0/-45/90/45/0/0/-45/45/-45/0/0/45/0/-45/90/-45/0/45/0/0/-45/45].

Engineering constant	Identification	Engineering constant	Identification
E_{11} /MPa	15370	X_t /MPa	2688
E_{22} /MPa	8295	X_c /MPa	1458
E_{33} /MPa	8295	Y_t /MPa	69.5
G_{12} /MPa	4370	Y_c /MPa	236
G_{23} /MPa	4370	Z_t /MPa	55.5
G_{13} /MPa	4370	Z_c /MPa	175
ν_{12}	0.32	S_{12} /MPa	136
ν_{23}	0.32	S_{23} /MPa	136
ν_{13}	0.32	S_{13} /MPa	95.6

Table 1: Material properties

No.	Ply Scheme	t_1 (mm)	Countersunk Fastener
A-01	[45/-45/0/-45/45/-45/45/90]s	3.008	CFBL1004AG8
			CFNT1001TB8
			NAS1149C0416R
A-02	[45/-45/0/-45/45/-45/45/90]s	3.008	CFBL1002AG8
			CFNT1003CY8
			NAS1149C0416R
B-01	[45/-45/0/-45/45/0/-45/45/90]s	3.384	CFBL1004AG8
			CFNT1001TB8
			NAS1149C0416R
B-02	[45/-45/0/-45/45/0/-45/45/90]s	3.384	CFBL1002AG8
			CFNT1003CY8
			NAS1149C0416R
C-01	[45/-45/0/0/-45/45/0/-45/45/90]s	3.76	CFBL1004AG8
			CFNT1001TB8
			NAS1149C0416R
C-02	[45/-45/0/0/-45/45/0/-45/45/90]s	3.76	CFBL1002AG8
			CFNT1003CY8
			NAS1149C0416R

Table 2: Specimens parameters

The bearing tests are conducted by MTS S10T. Each specimen has a extensometer (whose scale distance is 50 mm) fixed on both panel A and B. According to ASTM Standard D5961 [6], a standard head displacement rate of 2 mm/min is applied. The bearing force is created by loading the assembly in tension in a testing machine. Figure 2 describes the installation of specimens. Both the applied force and the associated deformation of the hole are monitored. The hole deformation is normalized by the hole diameter to create an effective bearing strain. The specimen is loaded until a maximum force has clearly been reached, whereupon the test is terminated so as to prevent masking of the true failure mode by large-scale hole distortion, in order to provide a more representative failure mode assessment. The deformation is recorded here by extensometer and the applied force is recorded by the testing machine.

Figure 2: Specimen installation

2.2 Results and Analysis

The stress-strain curves are obtained in accordance with ASTM Standard D5961 [6], which are shown in Figure 3.

Different features can be distinguished from Figure 2. For group A, the specimen A-01 presents a higher ultimate strength (905.4 MPa). There are several sliding sections in curve A-01, while curve A-02 has two significant turning points. The specimen 01 of group B and C also have higher ultimate strength compared with their contrast. The influences of countersunk fastener dimensions is further discussed in section 3.

Figure 3: Stress-strain curves of Group A, B and C

Similar features can also be distinguished from all the curves. It can be observed that all the curves can be divided into three parts approximately according to the slope of the curves. Both curves of the first and second stage are near-linear and the turning point is significant.

In the first stage, the countersunk fastener contacts well with internal surface of the hole since the preload exists. The specimens exhibit a high initial stiffness, which attributed to the static friction forces of the laminates [7]. Larger countersunk head provides better contact between the laminates and the fastener. Figure 4-a shows the test phenomenon of specimen A-02 corresponding to the first stage.

Figure 4-a: The test phenomenon corresponding to the first stage

In the second stage, the fastener deflects apparently as the composite being pressed. It can be seen in Figure 2 that the stress-strain is still near-linear, which indicates the deflection angle of the fastener is small (less than 5 degree) and the composite has no significant failure. Figure 4-b shows the test phenomenon corresponding to the second stage.

Figure 4-b: The test phenomenon corresponding to the second stage

In the third stage, crack can be heard as the tensile displacement increasing. The stiffness of the structure drops rapidly and turns to failure. The fastener has been distorted seriously. Delamination can be observed at the skin where the start of the countersunk fastener located. There exists secondary bending because of the offset of load, which contributed the complexity of the mechanical response. Figure 4-c shows the test phenomenon corresponding to the third stage.

Figure 4-c: The test phenomenon corresponding to the third stage

3 NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

Using ABAQUS[®] software, a 3D finite element model is established based on Hashin failure

criteria. Comparison with the test results proves the validity of the model. The effects of dimensions of countersunk fasteners on the bearing property of the joints are further studied by changing the parameters.

3.1 Finite Element Model

Specimen A-02 is selected to build the finite model for its typical stress-strain curve. To simplify the problem, only the un-gripped parts of the specimen are modeled.

Considering the countersunk bolt and nut as a whole body can also improve the computational efficiency and guarantee the precision. It is feasible to define fastener material as elasticity since the test has proved that composite failure and bolt torsion angle dominant the bearing property of the joints. The gasket material is given orthotropic thermal properties and thermally-expanded in the through-thickness direction to simulate the bolt pre-load instead of using the bolt load tool, which is not available in ABAQUS/Explicit module [8]. Figure 5 shows the simplified fastener model.

Figure 5: Semi-section of the countersunk fastener model.

Each layer of composite is modeled using a layer of orthotropic solid cell. Figure 6 shows the model of composite plate. The property and failure mode of composite material is simulated by ABAQUS Vumat based on Hashin criteria. Studies has proved that Hashin criteria can provide a good approximation of fiber failure [9]. The stiffness reduction criterion proposed by Papanikos et al [10] is used to describe the process damage.

Figure 6: The composite plate model

The penalty method is used to simulate surface to surface interaction. Based on the study by McCarthy et al [7], friction coefficients are $\mu = 0.7$ (laminate to laminate interaction); $\mu = 0.3$ (nut to laminate interaction); $\mu = 0.1$ (bolt to laminate interaction).

All the part instances are meshed by reduced integration elements [8] (C3D8R). The region near the contact surface has refined grids to improve the precision of the model. The final FE model is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Final setup model of the joints

3.2 Results and Analysis

The numerical calculation result is compared with experimental result to prove the validity. Figure 8 shows the stress-strain curves of both methodologies. The stress-strain curve obtained by FE model presents a good agreement with the experimental curve on the slope and ultimate strength. However, it is significant that the FE curve has a much shorter . This is caused by the loss of glass stiffness, which cannot be avoided.

Figure 8: Stress-strain curves of experimental and numerical results

ASTM Standard D5961 offers a method to define the effective region of stress-strain curve, which requests a offset stiffness line to seek out the offset strength [6]. The comparison between A-02 and FE model results is show in Table 3. It can be seen that FE has a 10.73% lower offset strength and a 6.05% higher ultimate strength, which is allowable.

	Offset Strength	Ultimate Strength
A-02	629.3 MPa	704.5 MPa
FE	561.8 MPa	747.1 MPa
Error Value	10.73%	6.05%

Table 3: Strength of experimental and numerical results

Corresponding to the three stage of experimental phenomenon, the damage propagation can be investigated more clear through the damage cloud, which is shown in Figure 9 and 10. In the first stage, few sliding exists between the two laminates, causing few damage in the structure. The preload of the fastener may lead to a little damage in some regions of stress concentration such as the edge of countersunk. In the second stage, matrix and fiber damage first appears at the edge between countersunk and straight contact surfaces and then extend to whole contact surface, especially where the 0°plies exist. It is worth noting that the upper surface and sub-surface of panel A present lots of damage. That is caused by concentrated stress applied by the sharp edge of countersink bolt. In the third stage, the contact surfaces have been seriously distorted. The laminates present a large region of matrix and fiber damage, which cause the steep decline of structure stiffness.

Figure 9: Damage propagation of matrix

Figure 10: Damage propagation of fiber

As the validity of FE model is proved, further study is conducted by changing the dimensions of countersunk fasteners. This shall be useful for the countersunk composite joints in engineering application.

Figure 11-a shows the stress-strain curves of FE-1-1 to FE-1-5 by the change of countersunk height to laminate thickness ratio h/t (here t means t_1 as shown in Figure 1) and Figure 11-b shows ultimate and offset strength. The offset stiffness of FE-1-1, FE-1-2 and FE-1-3 are similar, but the value of FE-1-4 and FE-1-5 become smaller. It can also be observed that the strength value goes larger first and then drops quickly. The reason of this drop is that the laminate where the countersunk head locates is going to have delamination more easily as h/t rises. If $h/t = 1$, which means the countersunk head is through all laminate thickness, delamination would be restrained, causing the rise of strength.

Figure 11-a: The stress-strain curves of FE-1-1 to FE-1-5

Figure 11-b: The ultimate and offset strength of FE-1-1 to FE-1-5

Figure 12-a shows the stress-strain curves of FE-2-1 to FE-2-3 and Figure 12-b shows the ultimate and offset strength. It is revealed that the change of countersunk angle θ from 60° to 120° impacts little on the offset stiffness of countersunk joints, but has a significant impact on the stiffness of the third stage. As the countersunk angle θ goes larger, the stiffness becomes larger as well as the ultimate

strength. The reason is that larger θ offers better contact between laminates and fasteners and avoids more initial damage caused by bolt torque.

Figure 12-a: The stress-strain curves of FE-2-1 to FE-2-3

Figure 12-b: The ultimate and offset strength of FE-2-1 to FE-2-3

4 CONCLUSION

An experimental and a numerical investigation has been conducted into the damage propagation

and strength of composites with single countersunk joints. The following conclusions can be drawn from the studies:

- The bearing process of single countersunk composite joints can be divided into three stages. The countersunk fastener dimensions demonstrate the turning point between every two stages.
- Initial damage appears first at the line between countersunk and straight contact surfaces and then extend to whole contact surface, especially where the 0° plies exist.
- With the rise of countersunk height to laminate thickness ratio h/t , the ultimate and offset strength goes larger first and then lower, but become larger when $h/t = 1$. The maximum strength appears at $h/t = 0.752$, approximately.
- As the countersunk angle θ goes larger, the stiffness becomes larger as well as the ultimate and offset strength. The θ has small effect on the offset strength but significant effect on the ultimate strength.

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